

CURE CYCLE ACCELERATION VIA NANO-DRIVEN THERMAL PROCESSING OF OUT-OF-AUTOCLAVE THERMOSETTING COMPOSITES

Frederick Daso¹, Jeonyoon Lee¹, Tomasz Garstka², Alan McMillan², and Brian L. Wardle¹

¹ Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, MA, United States of America,

² LMAT (Lean Manufacturing & Assembly Technologies) Limited, Bristol, United Kingdom

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) comprised of carbon microfiber reinforcement with thermoset and thermoplastic polymer matrices are increasingly utilized by aerospace companies for vehicle lightweighting. Traditional curing processes such as autoclaves and ovens rely on convective heat transfer, which has both inefficiencies and several limitations that may be overcome with direct (conductive) heating methods. Direct Joule heating with carbon nanotube (CNT) film network heaters has shown significant promise in overcoming inefficiencies in curing out-of-autoclave (OoA) prepreg CFRP. This Out-of-Oven (OoO) conductive curing technique is used here to cure aerospace-grade OoA CFRP prepreg laminates with equivalent quality to that achieved with the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle (MRCC) in an oven in a fraction of the time by taking advantage of the OoO heaters enhanced rate of heating to redesign the cure cycle utilizing finite element simulations.

1 INTRODUCTION

Use of autoclaves and ovens for processing thermosetting composites has issues related to their fixed size, with their thermal mass being significantly greater (relative to part mass) than other heating mechanisms (e.g., microwaves, radio frequency). The major limitation is convective heat transfer that can be used to explain why an autoclave or oven is slower – they involve thermal barriers in terms of the convective medium and also the cure materials (e.g., vacuum bag) that delay the heat from the oven or autoclave walls from getting to the part surface. In addition, a larger thermal mass (the oven or autoclave relative to the part) requires more energy in the form of heat to increase or decrease its temperature, slowing response time. Given the slow heating and cooling rates of these large heating chambers, cure cycles have been designed with these limitations in mind, with their dwell time being one or two hours to account for the thermal lag between the convective medium (usually air) within the chamber and the laminate being processed. OoO curing bypasses these barriers due to the CNT film's relatively rapid thermal response as current flows through the CNT network having extremely low thermal mass (areal density of ~ 25 g/m²), and the conductive nature of the heater being in contact with the part. The rapid heating rate of up to 12.3 °C/s allowed by the electrical and thermal properties of the CNT film allows for a cure cycle to be accelerated, which is two orders of magnitude faster than a typical autoclave's of 0.05 °C/s ramp rate [1]. In this work OoO fast curing is demonstrated for OoA CFRP thermosetting composites, reducing the traditional cure cycle by greater than 50% while still producing similar or better quality thermoset laminates than a traditional MRCC.

ANSYS Composite Cure Simulator (ACCS) was used to model an eight ply quasi-isotropic laminate of unidirectional Hexcel IM7/M56 OoA thermosetting prepreg to inform and design an accelerated cure cycle. By combining empirical data of cure kinetics with analytical solutions to generate simulations, this finite element analysis software can assist in rapid iteration to realize accelerated cure cycles. Relying on simulations saves time and effort on experimental work provided reasonable assumptions in the model and the validity of the results confirmed experimentally. Previous work from Lee et al. shows that ACCS prediction of the degree of cure using AS4/8552 inputs was

closely in line with results from their experimental tests of IM7/M56, and this finding is utilized here as IM7/M56 properties for ACCS modeling are not yet available [2].

2 EXPERIMENTAL

The objective of the modeling efforts in this study is to leverage powerful simulations to quickly iterate and find a cure cycle that decreases the time for full curing while still achieving an acceptable DoC (90-95%). To do this, ACCS requires interactions between many different self-contained modules (shown in Figure 1) to produce a full solution with the targeted outputs: the DoC and the cure cycle.

Figure 1: ACCS Workflow for accelerated cure simulations.

This workflow within ACCS has four discrete steps. First, determine the materials used within the Engineering Data module. Next, define the geometry of a single ply and a 6061 Aluminum metal tool plate in the Geometry module. The metal tool plates has a Young's Modulus, E , equal to 71.0 GPa and a thermal conductivity of $175 \frac{W}{m \cdot C}$. The initial geometry of a single ply was modeled in ACCS's SpaceModeler computer-aided design (CAD) program. Then, the quasi-isotropic layup of the laminate with two metal tool plates on the top and bottom of it was defined in the ANSYS Composite Pre (ACPre) module. Finally, the initial boundary conditions were defined and the accelerated cure cycle was applied to the laminate within the Transient Thermal module. Given that the resulting laminate was less than five millimeters in thickness, a fast solution method was used to solve the model [3].

Since the IM7/M56 material data was not available, the engineering data of AS4/8552 was used as a proxy in this study. Given that the cure cycle of IM7/M56 is identical to the cure cycle of AS4/8552, the latter can be used as a substitute. Each ply in the laminate is a 50 mm X 65 mm rectangle. The geometry was given a nominal thickness of 1 mm to allow a mesh to be created on it by editing in the Mechanical component system. With ACCS's mesh generator, a 63-element, 80-node mesh was created. Each element was a square with an edge length of 7.13 mm and a thickness of 1 mm. For the geometry, the 8-ply $[0/90/+45/-45]_s$ layup, had a nominal ply thickness of 0.253 mm, reflecting the nominal cured ply thickness of IM7/M56 [4]. Each ply had the AS4/8552 material data assigned to it. The quasi-isotropic ply layup sat in between two equal aluminum metal tool plates, each having a length of 65 mm, a width of 50 mm, and a thickness of 6.35 mm. The aluminum metal tool material is called "Aluminum Alloy" in ACCS and is used by the program for molding aluminum tools in curing composites. The metal thickness and boundary conditions match the experimental setup. The model now contained 891 nodes and 640 elements. The plate-laminate setup defined in ACPre was converted into a solid composite model, meaning a full model of the plates and composite as one, to allow applications of the cure cycle within the Transient Thermal module.

The initial temperature is set to be uniform at 20 °C. The temperature of the bottom of the lower metal tool plate is made to follow the MRCC. Setting up the heating in this manner simulates the conductive heat transfer from the CNT heater to the laminate through the aluminum plate in the experimental setup. Given that a thermal insulation is used in the experimental setup, the bottom surface was assumed to be perfectly insulated in the model. This simulates the lack of heat flowing from the bottom of the plate into the calcium silicate thermal insulation block below it in the

experimental setup. The calcium silicate used in the experiments has an isotropic thermal conductivity of $0.115 \frac{W}{m \cdot C}$ [5]. For reference, the metal tool plates and the composite in the through-thickness direction have thermal conductivities of $175 \frac{W}{m \cdot C}$ and $0.658 \frac{W}{m \cdot C}$, respectively.

The convective model to simulate the oven cure was built the same manner as described for the OoO fast-cured model with a two key differences. One, the bottom of the lower metal tool plate is heated via convection, not conduction in the OoO fast-cured model, with a heat transfer coefficient of $15 \frac{W}{m^2 \cdot C}$. Two, the Perfectly Insulated Heat Flow option was not applied to the bottom of lower metal tool plate as there is no thermal insulation underneath the metal tool plate in the Oven curing setup.

The setup for processing thermoset composite to fabricate specimens was based on a vacuum bag only (VBO) technique. A 305 mm (12") X 305 mm (12") X 3.175 mm (.125") thick base aluminum plate forms the foundation of the VBO setup. On top of the base plate rests a 152 mm (6") X 152 mm (6") X 25 mm (1") block of calcium silicate. The block functions as a thermal insulator to prevent the base plate from becoming a heat sink. On top, the block is a layer of guaranteed non-porous Teflon (GNPT) film from Airtech International. The GNPT film has two long strips of copper tape on its left and right edges. The commercial CNT film being used is from Veelo HEAT. The CNT film having dimensions of 150 mm X 150 mm lies on top of the GNPT film and copper strips, with care taken to maximize the area overlap of the interior edges of the copper strips on each side of the GNPT film. The CNT film was 150 mm X 150 mm to account for the area of the film covered by the Cu tape, as those regions generate no heat when the current flows through the film. Two more strips of copper tape are laid directly on top of the film and bottom two tape strips, securing the film in place to ensure contact with the copper to allow for current to flow easily. Another sheet of GNPT film is laid on top of the tape and film. This sheet is taped down using Flashbreaker-1 tape (thickness of 55 μ m, model #FB1272), which prevents the heater from moving. Cork tape (thickness of 6.25 mm) is used to form a "dam" with two interior areas that are 60 mm wide and 60 mm long for the two metal tool plates and laminates to be placed. Two 60 mm X 60 mm X 6.35 mm aluminum metal tool plates are placed in the open areas formed by the cork "dam."

The aluminum metal tool plates have one side covered in a sheet of GNPT film. The plies of the laminate are then laid one by one on a separate clean surface, and then the laminate is placed on top of the aluminum plate with GNPT film. Once all the plies are stacked on the plate, another layer of GNPT film is placed on the top ply. A thermocouple is placed close to the top edge of the GNPT film. Then a second tool plate is placed on top. High-temperature sealant tape from Airtech International is adhered around the perimeter of thermal insulation on top of the base plate. The copper tape strips are run across the width of the sealant tape to allow for wires to attach to them after the vacuum is pulled in the interior of the setup. Similarly, the thermocouple wiring is also run across the width of the sealant tape, where the connector attaches to a USB reader port. The USB thermocouple reader is then plugged into a laptop or desktop to read the temperature in real time.

A vacuum hose port is then placed on the bottom left corner of the square made from the sealant tape. Breather film is then placed on top of the laminate assembly, making sure to cover the vacuum port as well to allow for proper airflow from the laminate to the hose. A larger sheet of bagging film is then placed on top of the stack up and pressed down on the sealant tape to enclose the region of space for a vacuum to be established.

Once the bagging film is in place, the vacuum pump (Vacuubrand MD 1C) is turned on to pull vacuum within the bagging space. The wires from the positive and negative terminals of the power supply (BK Precision 9201) are clamped to the copper tape strips that protrude from the exterior of the setup that is now under vacuum pressure. Once the vacuum pressure reaches 28.5 in. Hg, the power supply is then turned on. The power output is managed from a graphical user interface of the manufacturer's software on the desktop via USB.

Accurate temperature control is needed to closely follow the fast cure cycle designed in ACCS. This is achieved by manual control of the voltage supply. For IM7/M56, the MRCC (which is the same as AS4/8552) for VBO processing as stated earlier and shown in Figure 2, while the experimentally realized temperature profile for OoO fast-curing is displayed in Figure 3. The voltage is raised from 0 to 22 volts, then decreased gradually by 0.5 volts every couple of minutes to maintain a heating rate of 10 °C /min until reaching 110 °C. Once that temperature is achieved, it is maintained for a dwell time of an hour to ensure proper resin flow and allow gelation to occur. After an hour, the power supply's voltage is increased to 27 volts to increase the temperature of the laminate at a rate of 10 °C /min to 200 °C. Then, the temperature will be maintained for twenty minutes by decreasing the voltage to 20 to 21 volts. After twenty minutes, the voltage is decreased to zero immediately, allowing the laminate to cool to room temperature via natural convective cooling in ambient conditions. The vacuum pump is turned off, and the bagging film and breather are removed to access the laminate. The top and bottom tool plates are manually separated from the laminate using a razor blade, and remnants of the GNPT on the sample are scraped off. For repeatability assessment of the fast cure cycle, three fast-cured OoO thermoset plates were produced. The end of the cure cycle is defined when the laminate temperature reaches 60 °C to calculate the cure cycle reduction.

The fabricated laminate is then cut into short beam shear (SBS) specimens with a diamond-grit wet saw [6]. For the SBS samples, following the American Society of Testing and Materials (ASTM) standard D2344, the dimensions based on the nominal thickness of an 8-ply specimen (nominal ply thickness is 0.253 mm) is 4.04 mm X 12.12 mm X 2.02 mm. The specimens are first cut in the middle of plate along with width-wise direction. Then, each half of the original plate is cut along the width-wise direction to obtain narrow slices for specimens to cut from the center of the plate. The narrow slices are then cut along the span-wise direction, and only five specimens from the center of each slice are selected as test coupons.

Once the specimens were cut, they were polished using sandpaper of various grits and water. Going by the American grit scale, the following sequence of sandpaper was used, from coarse to fine in terms of roughness: 400, 800, 1200. This particular polishing sequence with each type of sandpaper provided the best finish to image the surface of the fabricated test specimens optically. A Tegrapol-15 Struers Polishing Machine was used to polish each sample using water to wet the sandpaper while it grinded against the specimens at 300 rpm. The reason for polishing is two-fold: one, to remove scratches and any cracks from the cut surfaces of the specimens that might affect strength, and two, to remove dirt from cutting to allow the fiber and matrix to be seen clearly under an optical microscope. The first reason is important to mechanical testing, as the cracks on the specimen after cutting from a cured specimen could propagate under an applied load, thus allowing the material to fail earlier than it normally would. Once the specimens are polished, they are ready for the next set of tests to determine their quality and mechanical performance.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Starting with the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle (MRCC) in Figure 2, the convective (oven) model is solved and the resulting DoC is 91.6%. The goal is to create an accelerated cure that will allow us to achieve a similar degree of cure in a reduced amount of time. Easy candidates for modification in the MRCC are the one-hour dwell time at 110 °C and the two-hour dwell time at 180 °C. However, the most important factor in changing the MRCC would be the second heating ramp. The reason the second heating ramp is the critical factor is the rate of change of the DoC during this period. The DoC rate of change is maximized as the temperature rises from 110 °C to 180 °C. By increasing the ramp rate, the cure reaches its maximum value quicker. This decreases the need for two-hour second dwell time and allows for its reduction. The same rationale can be held for the first heating ramp, but to a lesser extent.

This understanding gleaned from studying the evolution of the degree of cure under the MRCC provided direction for developing an accelerated cure cycle. First, the second heating ramp was

increased from 1 °C/min to 10 °C/min for the OoO accelerated cure cycle. The OoO accelerated cure model was then solved to obtain the degree of cure output. Next, the second dwell temperature was increased from 180 °C to 200 °C. With an increased dwell temperature, the need for longer dwell time is reduced. The OoO accelerated cure model is once solved again, resulting in a fully cured laminate due to the two-hour dwell at 200 °C. The next obvious step was to reduce the two-hour dwell time – twenty minutes was tried. Once that adjustment was made, the OoO accelerated cure model was solved again, returning a degree of cure closer to results from earlier modified cure cycle solutions and the MRCC.

Figure 2: The MRCC for AS4/8552 applied to the flat plate in the Transient Thermal module in ACCS for the convective (oven) curing simulation.

Now, the first half of the modified cure cycle needs to be improved. However, unlike the second dwell temperature being increased by 20 °C, the first dwell temperature was maintained at 110 °C. In attempting to change the first half of the modified cure cycle, it was necessary to account for the viscosity of the resin during the gelation phase. The viscosity of the resin is not only dependent on temperature, but also the heating rate [8, 9]. Having increased the first heating ramp from 1 to 10 °C/min, the viscosity of the resin rapidly drops with the new heating rate versus the old one. If the resin’s viscosity becomes too low, excessive resin bleeding may occur. If viscosity is too high, then voids will not be removed during the cure. The model’s viscosity profile is based on a 1 °C/min heating rate, so the assumption that the viscosity of the resin would be lower in real life drove the decision to maintain current dwell temperature to not drive excessive resin bleeding because of an increased temperature. This results in the final accelerated cure cycle shown in Fig. 3 and the model was run again with these last two changes in place, resulting in a maximum DoC of 93.22% that was within ~1.5% of the traditional MRCC. The cure cycle reduction based on the simulations was determined by calculating the percent change of the accelerated cure cycle duration from the MRCC, resulting in 69%, as shown below.

$$\frac{20,640\text{ s} - 6,320\text{ s}}{20,640\text{ s}} = 69\% \tag{1}$$

Figure 3: The final accelerated cure cycle produced from ACCS. The duration of the cycle is 6,320 seconds, which is 69% less than the MRCC duration in the convective (oven) model

The model was run for a final time using the cure cycle shown in Figure 3, producing a maximum and minimum DoC of 93.22% and 92.84%, respectively (see Fig. 4). The accelerated cure cycle being only 6,320 seconds in duration, compared to 20,640 seconds for the MRCC. This faster cure cycle made possible by OoO curing represents a 69% reduction in the time necessary to sufficiently cure an OoA thermoset prepreg. This is a 3X acceleration in curing throughput.

Figure 4: DoC results for the accelerated cure cycle.

With the modeling results compiled, the accelerated cure cycle produced from the simulation and the MRCC are then followed experimentally in Figures 5 and 6.

Figure 5: Temperature profile of OoA sample cured via oven/MRCC.

Figure 6: Temperature profile of an OoA sample that underwent OoO fast-curing.

Performing the same calculations as in Equation 1 after Figure 2, the reduction in the cure cycle duration is 64%. The 5% difference between the simulation (69% reduction) and experimental time reduction is due to the natural convective cooling of the laminate in ambient conditions. After fabricating the specimens from each cure cycle for testing, sample quality assessment is performed to determine the DoC and void content.

Two factors are key to determining the manufacturing quality and mechanical performance of the fast-cured OoO specimens and their Oven counterparts: the DoC and void content. DoC for a thermoset resin is the measure of how much of the polymer has “cross-linked” or molecules forming networks of chemical bonds. Void content is also critical to assessing the quality of the composite, especially as it is a major factor in the mechanical performance of a test specimen⁵⁹⁻⁶¹. Generally, the

industry standard for aerospace-grade composites has a void content of less than 2% of the total volume of the sample. In some cases, particularly autoclave prepreg, this standard is lowered to 1% or less dependent on how critical the part is for the successful operation of a structure.

To determine the DoC for a cured sample, differential scanning calorimetry was performed in the same manner on the samples of the fabricated thermoset MRCC and fast-cured specimens. As the thermoset sample temperature increases, there will be an exothermic peak. By measuring the area underneath the curve of the exothermic peak on the thermograph, one obtains the heat of reaction of the sample. The heat of reaction is needed to calculate the degree of cure using the well-known formula:

$$\text{Degree of Cure} = \left(1 - \frac{\Delta H_{\text{uncured}}}{\Delta H_{\text{cured}}}\right) \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

ΔH_{cured} represents the total heat of reaction. $\Delta H_{\text{uncured}}$ represents the partial heat of reaction of an uncured prepreg sample cured to 100%. Three DSC samples each were obtained from the oven/MRCC and each of the three (sets 1 through 3) OoO fast-cured sample plates. Two DSC samples were cut from the uncured OoA IM7/M56 prepreg material. These samples were weighed on a mass balance, with the masses ranging from four to nine milligrams. The TA Instruments containers used to hold these samples were Tzero Aluminum Lids and Pans. These were also weighed on a mass balance. The masses for each sample, lid, and pan were recorded in a notebook before the DSC experiments. The instrument used in these experiments was a TA Instruments Discovery DSC machine. The temperature cycle used was heating from 25 °C to 350 °C at 5 °C/min, followed by a 1-minute dwell at 350 °C, then a cooling ramp back down to 25 °C at 50 °C/min. The results showed the OoO DSC specimens' degree of cure was around ~92%, which is in line with results from literature and the manufacturer's recommendation of an acceptable DoC within 90-95%.

Figure 7: The oven/MRCC and OoO fast-curing DoC results.

The OoO Cured Sets #1, #2, and #3 correspond to three quasi-isotropic plate samples made following the accelerated cure that was developed in ACCS in Figure 5.8 and experimentally produced Figure 5.12. It is important to note that Set #3 had the +45 and -45 plies swapped by accident. Not only are the OoO fast-cure DoC values in line with the oven/MRCC values, but also the values are consistent across the three sets, showing the repeatability of the fast cure cycle. Finally, the average thickness of the Oven set was 1.68 mm, while the average thickness for the OoO fast-cured Set #2 and #3 was 1.62 and 1.61 mm, respectively. The

standard error (SE) for the thicknesses of Set #2 and 3 is 0.016 mm and 0.0027 mm, respectively. The SE range (mean \pm SE) for the two Sets overlap, therefore they are statistically the same. It is important to note that the OoO fast-cured Set #1 was not used for SBS testing – only for DSC runs to obtain a DoC. With the degree of cure of the OoO accelerated cured specimens in line with conventionally produced specimens, examining the void content is key from a performance perspective to fully confirm the quality of these alternatively-cured test coupons.

The void content in a composite laminate plays a major role in its overall strength under load — the more voids in a composite, the greater the reduction in strength⁵⁹⁻⁶¹. Voids allow stress concentrations to build up in the epoxy matrix, which is the weakest part of the laminate. These stress concentrations lead to cracks, which will propagate under increased load. The cracks can result in delamination of the plies, resulting in the composite losing its stiffness and load-bearing capability.

A ZEISS Xradia 520 Versa 3D X-ray Microscope was used to reveal the microstructure of a scanned specimen to quantify the void content in a given test coupon. A metal stand was used to hold the specimen in place. The stand was placed on a stage within the interior of the Versa where it would rotate in front of the source to have X-rays penetrate it and capture the resulting images through the detector.

For each method (OoO fast-curing and oven/MRCC), three SBS specimens were scanned in the Versa microscope. The objective used was 0.4X for all the specimens except the last specimen from each curing method's set. The scans at the objective setting of 0.4X were for checking the void content of the scanned specimens to confirm the specimens were void free. The last specimen was scanned using an objective of 4X, which decreased the pixel size from 4.7 μm to roughly 1.5 μm , providing a high-resolution image of the individual fibers dispersed about the matrix. Once the specimens were scanned, the images depicting their microstructure were analyzed with ImageJ. The brightness and contrast was adjusted to only focus on two different peaks; the first represented the voids in the image, and the second corresponded to the fiber-matrix consisting of the rest of the picture. By isolating these two peaks, the area of the voids could be identified, and then divided by the area of the whole image to obtain the void content for a single image. This was done for twenty images for each specimen. Microcomputed tomography images are shown in Figures 5.14 and 5.15 for the oven/MRCC and OoO fast-cured specimens at the 1.5 μm pixel resolution, respectively. The results show no detectable voids above a pixel size of 1.5 μm for the both the Oven-cured and fast cured SBS OoO specimens. For all sets cured either via oven/MRCC or OoO fast-cured, the void content is zero.

Figure 8: Left image: microcomputed tomography image of an oven/MRCC quasi-isotropic SBS specimen. The specimen is void free. Right image: Microcomputed tomography image of an OoO fast-curing quasi-isotropic SBS specimen. The specimen is void free.

Figure 9: Left image: Representative load-displacement curves for the oven/MRCC and OoO fast-curing specimens of set #2 from SBS testing. Right image: A comparison of the short beam strengths of the oven/MRCC and OoO fast-curing specimens of set #2.

Figure 10: Left image: representative load-displacement curves of the oven/MRCC and OoO fast-curing (Swapped) specimens of set #3 from SBS testing. It is important to note that the “swapped” label indicates that the +45 and -45 plies were accidentally switched during the layup process of this particular set of OoA OoO fast-cured quasi-isotropic SBS specimens. Right image: A comparison of the short beam strengths of the oven/MRCC and OoO fast-curing (swapped) specimen of set #3.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Leveraging the near-instantaneous thermal response of commercial CNT film has made it possible to shorten the MRCC for OoA CFRP laminates. FEA models allowed rapid development of an accelerated cure cycle for OoA laminates that achieve the same DoC. These cure cycles from the simulations were implemented in the experimental work to produce void-free laminates as evaluated via microcomputed tomography. DSC showed that the OoO fast-cured sample sets had similar DoCs compared to the conventional oven-cured samples. SBS testing revealed no statistical difference between the specimens of the OoO fast-cured sets #2 and #3 and the oven-made samples. As mentioned before, OoO fast-cured Set #1 was not used for SBS testing, only for obtaining the DoC for repeatability concerns. Further work can be done to shorten the cure cycle, especially by altering the ramp rates and the dwell temperature and time of the first hold in the cure cycle. OoO curing allows one to reduce the cure cycle time by 64% experimentally, from nearly six hours to a little more than two hours for thermosetting laminates made of IM7/M56, while still producing high-quality laminates and test specimens. Further acceleration may be possible utilizing the methodology introduced here.

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